

MICROMECHANICAL FAILURE ANALYSIS FOR COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A micromechanics analysis of failure is given for Unidirectional Fibre-Reinforced Composites (UFRC), based on the assumption that the UFRC may be generally represented by an assembly of triply concentric composite cylinders. This model previously used to determine the mechanical properties of UFRC is composed of a single fibre surrounded by a cylindrical matrix together with an interfacial sheath between them. All three phases are allowed to have cylindrical anisotropy. The micro-stresses and strains are then found for this representative composite cylinder. Finally, an appropriate failure criterion is proposed for each anisotropic constituent phase and, consequently, the failure of UFRC is assessed. As an illustration of the proposed micromechanical failure analysis, a comparison of the prediction of the failure of a graphite/epoxy UFRC is made with that due to the normal phenomenological, macromechanical approach.

INTRODUCTION

The failure analysis of composites is one of the most important ingredients in the design of structures made of advanced composites. The key features of such a failure analysis are the selection of an appropriate failure theory and the ability to perform stress analysis for composite structures. During the last decade, the anisotropy of advanced composites has been increasingly used to tailor their elastic properties in, for example, laminate structures. However, due to the high anisotropy and inhomogeneity of composites, the failure mechanism and the stress analysis for them are much more complicated than that for homogeneous isotropic materials. In fact, even for a uniaxial tensile failure specimen, different modes of failure and stress singularities can be observed due to the interaction between the different constituent materials. Owing to the importance and complexity of the subject, a large literature dealing with different aspects of failure in composites has accumulated during the last two decades. Generally speaking, the different approaches adopted for the failure characterisation of composites can be broadly classified into micromechanical and macromechanical approaches.

For example, on the one hand, Chamis¹ has advocated the use of a simplified analytical approach to the microstress and failure analysis of laminates; while Adams et al² has applied finite element analysis. A more detailed review of the micromechanical failure analysis of composites has been given recently by Pindera³. The progress made by using the micromechanics approach is still much more limited than that with the macromechanics approach. The majority of failure theories for composite structures have used the macromechanics approach due to its relative simplicity. A great amount of work on macromechanics failure analysis has been documented. For example, an extensive review was given by Rowland⁴. But, as pointed out in the authors' previous work⁵, macromechanical failure theories have been unable to successfully predict the true failure modes and strengths of

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composites. It is believed that a micromechanics failure analysis, despite more complicated stress analysis and elaborate failure theories are required for these predictions.

In the present work, a micromechanical failure analysis is presented for a three phase unidirectional fibre-reinforced composite, of which all three phases are considered to be cylindrical anisotropic. This analysis is mainly based on the concept⁶ that the realistic composite material can be well simulated by an assembly of representative volume elements and on the use of the micromechanics failure theory previously proposed by the authors⁵ for fully anisotropic composites. Here, a triply-concentric composite cylinder, composed of a single fibre and a matrix cylinder with an interfacial sheath between them, is taken as such a representative volume element. Using this simple model, the general relations between the loading conditions and the constituent stiffness and volume fraction is then set up by performing a detailed microstress and strain analysis⁷. Consequently, the true strength of the UFRG can be predicted together with the knowledge of how and where failure is initiated with the aid of the appropriate failure criterion applied to each of the individual constituent phases.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

1. Triply Concentric Cylinder Model and Basic Assumptions

As stated earlier, the three phase unidirectional fibre-reinforced composite under consideration is to be modelled by a triply-concentric composite cylinder as shown in Fig. 1. From Fig. 1, the following geometric relationships are seen to hold:

$$v_f = r_f^2 / r_m^2$$

$$v_i = (r_i^2 - r_f^2) / r_m^2$$

and

$$v_m = (r_m^2 - r_i^2) / r_m^2$$

with $v_f + v_i + v_m = 1$

where r_f , r_i and r_m are the outer radii of the fibre, the interfacial material and the matrix, respectively; and v_f , v_i and v_m are, respectively, their volume fractions.

Fig. 1 A triply-concentric composite cylinder composed of (a) a single fibre; (b) an interfacial sheath and (c) a matrix cylinder

Strictly speaking, an assembly of a number of such triply-concentric composite cylinders should be considered and the spatial array of this assembly should be examined. But, it has been shown in previous work^{8,9,10} that there is little loss of accuracy using the assumption of periodicity in predicting the effective mechanical properties of composite materials and this will be used here. Additionally, perfect bonding between fibre, interface and matrix are assumed and all these constituents are considered to be linearly elastic to failure.

2. Stress Analysis for Triply-concentric Composite Cylinder

From the previous section, the composite cylinder itself can also be considered to be of cylindrical anisotropy. Hence, the stress-strain relations for the composite and its constituents (fibre, interface and matrix) can then all be written in the cylindrical coordinate system in the same form¹¹

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_r^k \\ \epsilon_\theta^k \\ \epsilon_z^k \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_r^k & -\nu_{\theta r}^k/E_\theta^k & -\nu_{zr}^k/E_z^k \\ -\nu_{r\theta}^k/E_r^k & 1/E_\theta^k & -\nu_{z\theta}^k/E_z^k \\ -\nu_{rz}^k/E_r^k & -\nu_{\theta z}^k/E_\theta^k & 1/E_z^k \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_r^k \\ \sigma_\theta^k \\ \sigma_z^k \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where E's and ν 's are the normal engineering constants, the superscript k (k=c,f,i,m) stands for the composite, fibre, interfacial material and matrix respectively. The resultant explicit formulations for calculating the true (micro) stress/strain distributions for the composite cylinder, under longitudinal (in the fibre direction) and transverse loadings, are described in detail elsewhere⁷. From this the following results may be quoted.

A. Longitudinal loading condition

In this case, the cylinder is subjected to a uniformly distributed axial (fibre direction) strain, ϵ_0 . Hence, the microstress solution to this generalized plane strain problem can be written in the following general form

$$\sigma_j^k = f_j^k (E's, \nu's, u's, r) \epsilon_0 \quad (k=f,i,m; j=r,\theta,z) \quad (2)$$

where f_j^k stands for the general function of the engineering constants (E's, ν 's), volume fractions (u's) and radial coordinates of the constituents. The specific forms for f_j^k are given in equations (7), (8) and (15) of reference 8.

B. Transverse loading condition

In this case the cylinder is subjected to a uniformly distributed radial surface traction, σ_0 . Hence, the microstress solution to this normal plane strain problem can again be written in the general form

$$\sigma_j^k = \psi_j^k (E's, \nu's, u's, r) \sigma_0 \quad (k=f,i,m; j=r,\theta,z) \quad (3)$$

Similarly, ψ_j^k in equation (3) stands for the functions of the constituents' properties, volume fractions and radial-coordinate. Its specific form is derived using equations (7), (8) and (17) of reference 8.

Additionally, in both cases, the microstrain can be directly calculated using the stress-strain relation (1) and solution (2) or (3). It is seen that the loading condition (at the macro-level) has been explicitly related to the constituent's properties and its true stress/strain (at the micro-level). Hence, the failure modes can be readily identified using these true stress/strain solutions with the aid of the appropriate micromechanical failure criteria. Consequently, the strength of UFRCC can be generally predicted together with the knowledge of how and where failure is initiated. In what follows, we develop the micromechanical failure criteria for the UFRCC.

3. Micromechanical Failure Criterion

Though the study of the failure mechanisms of composites is complex, it is generally agreed that the different types of failure can, in principle, be differentiated into (i) fibre failure; (ii) matrix failure and (iii) interface failure. Hence, the failure criteria to be developed should be individually addressed to these constituent materials. In addition, it is known that all three different types of failure may still exist even for one single loading condition (e.g. transverse

tension) due to the inhomogeneity and anisotropy of UFRC. Hence, the desired failure criterion should also be developed in a manner that can take into account the effect of all stress/strain components and differences in tensile and compressive responses on the failure envelope. For this simple analysis, given that the linear-elastic assumption was made at the beginning for all the constituents, only brittle or initial yielding can be catered for. Thus, the failure of all three constituents can be generally described either by a stress-to-failure function, F_{σ}^k , of the following form

$$F_{\sigma}^k(\sigma_j^k, \alpha_k) = 1 \quad (4)$$

or the strain-to-failure function, F_{ϵ}^k , of the form

$$F_{\epsilon}^k(\epsilon_j^k, \beta_k) = 1 \quad (5)$$

In the failure criteria (4) or (5), α_k or β_k are the experimentally measured parameters mainly related to each constituent's principal strengths or ultimate strains. Obviously, the specific forms of F_{σ}^k or F_{ϵ}^k not only depend upon the modes of failure of the constituents, but also upon the practicability and reliability of the techniques to measure the parameter α_k or β_k particularly for fibres. As an example, from previous work⁷, these specific forms may be written in the form

$$P_i^f \epsilon_i^f + P_{ij}^f \epsilon_i^f \epsilon_j^f = 1 \quad (i, j=1, 2, \dots, 6) \quad (6)$$

for fibre failure and

$$P_i^m \sigma_i^m + P_{ij}^m \sigma_i^m \sigma_j^m = 1 \quad (i, j=1, 2, \dots, 6) \quad (7)$$

for matrix failure.

Hence, by determining the true stresses and strains of the constituents with the criterion (4) or (5), the failure point and failure mode can be identified within the UFRC and strength of UFRC can then be evaluated.

APPLICATION

As an illustration of the proposed micromechanical approach to the failure analysis of UFRC, the ultimate strength of a triply-concentric composite cylinder, composed of a Hercules As-graphite fibre, a Hercules 3501-6 epoxy matrix and an artificial interface material (due to lack of experimental data for its properties), is studied and compared with that due to the normal phenomenological, macromechanical approach. The properties of fibre and matrix are cited directly from reference 2, whereas averages of these are taken as properties for the interface. The required properties of these constituents are then given in Table 1

Table 1 Constituent material properties of the example composite cylinder

Property	Graphite fibre	Epoxy matrix	Artificial interface
Longitudinal modulus, E_z (GPa)	220	4.3	112.15
Transverse modulus, E_r (GPa)	14	4.3	9.15
Major Poisson's ratio, $\nu_{r\theta}$	0.20	0.34	0.26
In-plane Poisson's ratio, $\nu_{r\theta}$	0.25	0.34	0.295
Longitudinal tensile strength, σ_z^u (MPa)	3100	83	1591
Transverse tensile strength, σ_r^u (MPa)	345	83	214

A fibre volume fraction of 30% and an interface volume fraction of 5% are assumed, while the unit composite cylinder geometry is considered. Hence, the outer radii of fibre, interface and matrix are: $r_f = 0.548$, $r_i = 0.592$ and $r_m = 1.0$. In addition,

in this example, only the simplest form of the criterion (4) or (5), i.e. that of the maximum stress form, is adopted in the following calculation of the failure strength for the example cylinder. To calculate the stresses under longitudinal loading we apply a constant strain, ϵ_0 , equivalent to the assumption of perfect bonding. Thus, the allowable axial strain, ϵ_a , is determined by

$$\epsilon_a = \min\{(\sigma_j^u)_k / \max f_j^k\} \quad (k \equiv f, i, m ; j \equiv r, \theta, z) \quad (8)$$

under longitudinal loading, and the allowable radial traction, σ_a , is given by

$$\sigma_a = \min\{(\sigma_j^u)_k / \max \phi_j^k\} \quad (k \equiv f, i, m ; j \equiv r, \theta, z) \quad (9)$$

under transverse loading.

Consequently, using the formulation (8) and (9) with the constituent properties listed in Table 1, ϵ_a and σ_a are calculated and compared with that due to the normal macromechanics maximum stress theory where a rule of mixtures assumption is used to calculate modulus and strengths. These are respectively tabulated in Table 2.

Table 2 Comparison of micromechanics with macromechanics approach to the allowable axial strain, ϵ_a , and radial traction, σ_a , of a graphite/epoxy cylinder subjected to longitudinal and transverse loadings

Failure criterion	Allowable axial strain ϵ_a	Allowable radial traction σ_a (GPa)
micromechanics approach	0.0141 (f)	0.0773 (m)
macromechanics approach	0.0143	0.1120

Note: f, m in the bracket mean the fibre and matrix failure respectively

It is interesting, from Table 2, to note the following two points. First, in the case of longitudinal loading, a lower value of ϵ_a is predicted by the micromechanics approach than that due to the macromechanics approach. The two values are very close indicating that the fibre dominates the strength of the composite in the longitudinal direction, as expected. Secondly, in the case of transverse loading, the failure mode is matrix cracking (or debonding) along the fibre direction at the boundary between matrix and interface. In this case the role of the interface is to reduce the degree of the stress concentration. It is seen, from Table 2, that there is a great variation in the prediction of the allowable radial traction by the two approaches, and the higher value of σ_a again results from using the normal maximum theory. The macromechanics approach therefore significantly overestimate the transverse strength. Further comparison with experiment is required and this is the subject of future work.

CONCLUSIONS

A micromechanics approach to the failure analysis of UFRC is proposed on the basis of the representation of UFRC by a triply-centric composite cylinder and the analytical determination of microstress/strain distributions for this mode. Though the full verification of the proposed approach can not be made without comparison with experimental work, the primary results presented in this short paper show that reasonably accurate prediction of the strength of UFRC can be obtained and, most importantly, that the failure modes can be identified. In addition the consideration of cylindrical anisotropy for all constituents provides the designer of composite structures with greater ability to tailor the properties of advanced composites. The inclusion of an interface in this model enables the study of effects of imperfect bonding between fibre and matrix. Further experimental work is required to differentiate between the benefits of the micromechanical and macromechanical

approaches. Finally, the procedure used in this approach can be generalized to include the analysis of inelasticity and plastic failure by incorporating the appropriate loading functions into the present analysis where all constituents are individually subjected to different failure criteria.

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